

POTENTIALS AND BARRIERS OF MULTI-ENERGY-SYSTEMS FOR PROVISION OF FLEXIBILITY TO POWER MARKETS

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1 Motivation

The European Union's 2030 targets for renewable energy, greenhouse gas emission and energy efficiency require significant changes in the energy system. There is a growing need for additional flexibility to ensure the reliable and efficient operation of the electricity system due to the increasing share of fluctuating renewable power generation and the difficulties in generation forecasting. The project MAGNITUDE [1] investigates the possibilities of multi-energy-systems (MES) to provide flexibility to the power system based on the experiences of higher time constants, higher inertia and inherent resilience of gas and heat/cold networks compared to electricity networks. Enhanced synergies between different energy carriers appear as possible means to provide flexibility to the electricity system but also to drive efficiency and business innovation in the energy sector as a whole. [1]

The investigations in the project focus on seven case studies in different European countries: paper industry (Austria), steel industry (UK), large- and small-scale district heating systems and heat supply (Italy, Denmark), wastewater treatment and sewage gas exploitation (Spain), and district heating and cooling supply (France, Sweden).

The present paper explains the ongoing investigations and first results for the Austrian case study of a steam system in an integrated pulp and paper mill.

2 Modelling the steam system of the pulp and paper mill

It is proven practice, that industrial consumers of electricity and heat, which operate a combined heat and power (CHP) unit can shift the consumption between electricity and gas within certain limits based on an economic optimization. In many cases the CHP operation is guided by the heat demand of the facility and the generated electricity is used to supply local power consumers; the difference between power local power generation and consumption is exchanged with the public grid. The objective of the investigations was to describe the possibilities of the CHP and steam system to provide flexibility to the power system, with the

aim to meet the requirements of ancillary service markets for automatic Frequency Restoration Reserve (aFRR) and manual Frequency Restoration Reserve (mFRR) in Austria.

Figure 1 gives an overview of the possible consumption shift between gas and power network for the case of a net power consumer, i.e. the MES will consumer more electricity than generated by the CHP.

Figure 1: Overview of provision of positive and negative balancing energy by a MES which is a net electricity consumer.

The steam system applied in the investigated paper mill can be considered as a typical industrial steam system with different primary fuels, back-pressure steam turbines, and heat (steam) demand on different pressure levels (high-, mid-, and low-pressure). The investigations started with modelling the existing steam system and in-depth calculation of the technical feasibility to provide flexibility to the power grid during different states of operation. Even though the steam turbines produce a considerable amount of the electricity demand; the paper mill is still a net consumer of electricity from the public grid. Flexibility to the power system can be provided by shifting consumption between the power and the gas grid.

In case of provision of positive balancing energy, the boilers increase gas consumption and high-pressure (HP) steam generation. The additional HP steam is increasing the power generation in the turbine, which results in reduced net consumption from the power network. The additional amount of low-pressure steam cannot be used on-site and must be blown over the roof, which is a major drawback.

If negative balancing energy is requested, the gas flow to the boilers and the steam generation can be reduced, and the steam flow to the turbine can be controlled by means of bypass valves. As a result, the electricity consumption from the public network is increased while the gas consumption from the public grid is reduced in parallel.

2.1 Investigation of the steam network

Figure 2 presents a schematic diagram of the steam system design, which consists of three pressure tiers:

- 1) High pressure (HP) steam at 72 bar_g and steam temperature of 505 °C;
- 2) Medium pressure (MP) steam at 12 bar_g and steam temperature of 210 °C;
- 3) Low pressure (LP) steam at 3.5 bar_g and steam temperature of 190 °C.

Two boilers generate HP steam: 1) The gas boiler can regulate its steam output rapidly, which follows the variation of steam demand; 2) The recovery boiler is mainly fuelled by organic residue from the pulp production processes and supplemented by natural gas. The amount of steam generated by the recovery boiler depends on the pulp production processes and is considered as inflexible. The boiler feedwater is at 100 bar_g pressure and 104°C.

Steam demands are served at MP and LP tiers. A back-pressure steam turbine with MP steam extraction produces mechanical energy from the steam expansion process, namely HP steam to MP steam (HP → MP) and HP steam to LP steam (HP → LP). The steam turbine is coupled to a generator to provide electricity to supply on-site consumers. During normal operation, steam passing through the turbine is regulated by the steam demand that needs to be served for the paper production processes mainly as LP steam. Electricity generation is considered as a by-product. Any surplus/deficit between the on-site electricity generation and the electricity demand of the site is balanced by the public power grid. In fact, the investigated facility is a net consumer of electricity during the entire year.

Two by-pass valves are used to convert HP steam to MP and LP steam when required. Under normal conditions, these valves are activated when the steam turbine is not operational or when the steam demand exceeds the capacity of the steam turbine. A blow-off steam valve at the LP tier releases any excess steam from the system.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of the steam system

In this paper, flexibility is considered as the ability to change the electricity output of the turbine generator as illustrated in Figure 3. The steam system is able to provide flexibility to balance renewable generation or to participate in the Austrian mFRR or aFRR markets. From the perspective of the MES, this flexibility provision is achieved by shifting energy consumption between the public networks of electricity and gas.

Figure 3. Flowchart of upward and downward regulations.

2.1.1 Upward regulation

Upward regulation is implemented by increasing the on-site electricity generation via the following procedures: 1) If any by-pass steam flows are present (HP→MP or HP→LP), then the by-pass steam is reduced, so that the steam flow through the turbine increases. 2) If there is no by-pass steam flow or the upward regulation requirement is not met by reducing the by-pass flow to zero, then the steam production of the gas boiler is increased. The additional LP steam production may create excess steam in the system that needs to be removed using the blow-off valve in the LP steam system. Blowing excess steam over the roof is an undesired consequence, which causes environmental and economic disadvantages. From the system perspective, the increase in electricity generation causes a decrease of net consumption and is coupled with increased gas consumption.

2.1.2 Downward regulation

Downward regulation is implemented by reducing the on-site electricity generation via the following procedures: 1) If blow-off steam exists, then the gas boiler steam production is reduced to minimise the blow-off steam and thereby the steam flow rate through the turbine is reduced. 2) Open by-pass valves to re-route part of the steam flow outside of the turbine. The HP→LP by-pass valve is activated first due to its high efficiency. From the system's perspective, the downward regulation increases the net consumption and in parallel decreases the gas consumption.

2.2 Approach for technical simulation

Figure 4 shows a schematic diagram of the model. The inputs to the model include steam demands of the production processes, the flow rate of the blow-off steam, the flow rate of the by-pass steam, steam production of the recovery boiler, the flow rate of the black-liquor, total electricity demand on-site, and flexibility requirements of the power grid. Technical

characteristics of the steam system are obtained from design parameters and historical data and are pre-defined in the model. Outputs of the model are on-site electricity generation, imported electricity from the public power grid, imported gas from the public gas grid, variations of by-pass steam flows, and variations of blow-off steam flow resulted from flexibility provision.

Figure 4. Model description of the steam and electricity generation system

2.3 Results

2.3.1 Validation of the simulation model

In the following, the real operation data of a spring week (1 min granularity) are presented and compared with the simulation results for the same period. The steam consumers Paper Machine 3 (PM3), Paper Machine 4 (PM4), Evaporator (EVA), digester (YZG) and other LP steam demands are connected to the LP steam system. Pulp machine recovery boiler is connected to the MP steam system. Figure 5 shows the steam demand of the paper mill for this week.

Figure 5. Steam demands of the paper mill.

Figure 6 shows the comparison of the model output and the real operation data for the turbine generator and the gas boiler. The Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) is used to quantify the accuracy of the model. The MAPE of the electricity output of the turbine generator is 1.82%. The MAPE of the gas consumption of the boiler is 4.63%. The model output for electricity generation matches closely with real operation data over the week.

Figure 6. Performance comparison of the measured value and the model output.

2.3.2 The relation between flexibility and actual generation of the steam turbine

The model is used to quantify the maximum upward and downward regulation available at every time step, considering the various operating condition of the system (i.e. steam and electricity demand, the electricity generation of the turbine). Figure 7 shows the actual value and maximum flexibility of the electricity output of the turbine generator over the week. It can be seen that the steam system has certain flexibility for both upward regulation and downward regulations.

Figure 7. The flexibility of the electricity generation of the turbine for upward and downward regulations.

2.3.3 Investigation of improvement of the facility

A discussion of five technical improvement options showed that the installation of a steam accumulator is the most promising option to increase energy efficiency and flexibility provision from the paper mill.

A steam accumulator is being studied to improve the performance of the steam system. The objectives of installing the steam accumulator include:

- 1) Primary: To reduce steam blown over the roof to a minimum;
- 2) Secondary: To reduce peak costs for power and gas consumption;
- 3) Tertiary: To increase the flexibility of the steam turbine-generator for the power grid.

The investigated setup considers a steam accumulator, which is connected to the MP and LP systems shown in Figure 2. The volume of the steam accumulator is 270 m³; the liquid level inside the accumulator varies between 71% and 82.5% of the height. The maximum charging/discharging flow rate is assumed to be 20 t/h. For discharging, the steam accumulator releases its steam to the LP system directly; for charging, the MP steam is injected into the steam accumulator. The steam accumulator is used for smoothing the steam production of the gas boiler and to avoid blow-off. The total steam demand is maintained at a pre-determined level according to the demand forecast.

Currently, simulations are ongoing to identify the optimal volume and operation of the steam accumulator from a technical and economic perspective. The comparison of the simulation of the operation of the paper mill with and without steam accumulator will show the impact of the steam accumulator in terms of energy efficiency, fuel and electricity costs and the revenues from participation in the abovementioned flexibility markets.

3 Practical implications of flexibility provision by MES

An analysis of the characteristics of the existing flexibility markets in Austria [2] showed that the steam system could indirectly support renewable integration by offering flexibility to the following markets: aFRR, mFRR, intra-day or day ahead.

The participation in Austrian ancillary service markets requires a prequalification by the Transmission System Operator *Austrian Power Grid* (APG). In the last years, APG proved to be supportive to industrial flexibilities. Compared to the requirements for pure generators, there are no major barriers for participation of flexible consumers arising from the prequalification process [3,4].

It is an aim of the EU's energy policy to establish market-based mechanisms in most parts of the energy trading and supply system where possible. Industrial consumers can get access to the electricity markets for aFRR, mFRR, intra-day and day ahead directly or via traders or aggregators. While many analyses focus on the market prices, industrial consumers of electricity and natural gas in Austria have to bear additional costs for energy procurement, which are related to consumer taxes, network tariffs, and renewables support. Further, indirect costs may arise from carbon dioxide emissions or energy efficiency regulations but are not considered in the following descriptions below.

All energy consumers in Austria have to pay a dedicated energy charge (Energieabgabe) on consumption of electricity and gas which is regulated in the Elektrizitätsabgabegesetz [5] and Erdgasabgabegesetz [6]. The energy charge is stipulated with 0,015 EUR/kWh for electricity and ca. 0,0066 EUR/kWh (considering a gas levy of 0,066 EUR/m³ at 0°C and 1,01325 bar) for natural gas and lower heating value. The stipulated values can lead to a distortion in the optimization of the MES operation, because the charge for gas is only 44% of the charge for electricity. Since the marginal ratio of shift between electricity and gas (defined by the efficiency of boiler, CHP and gas network) in an industrial CHP usually is much better than 44%, the downward control is penalized while the upward control is incentivized by the energy charge. In case of significant energy costs compared to the production value of the producing enterprise, the Energieabgabenvergütungsgesetz [7] can be applied, which limits the energy charge with 0,5% of the net production value. As such, in case of an energy-intensive production the energy charge may not play a major role in the daily operation of the industrial MES because the limit will be reached anyhow.

Some components of the grid tariffs can have large influence on the operation of MES. Grid tariffs for electricity and gas are determined based on the monthly energy consumption and metered peak load in the month. The peak load is determined by the highest metered 15 min-average consumption of electricity and highest gas consumption during 1 h in a month. The Electricity System Charges Ordinance [8] and Gas System Charges Ordinance [9] and stipulates the system charges per region (distribution system operator) and grid level; as such a general conclusion for the entire country is not possible. In the investigated industrial MES, the network tariffs for electricity had a more than 3-times higher impact than the network tariffs for gas. The network tariffs raised the procurement costs of electricity by 15-30%, depending on the actual price of energy. In general, the operator of the MES will try to optimize the operation in order to avoid unnecessary peak consumption of electricity and gas. Provision of flexibility will contradict this aim because the peak load will be increased either in the gas or

electricity network. Since network tariffs for electricity are ca. 3-times higher than for gas, the negative balancing energy will face a higher cost burden from peak charges than the positive balancing energy. This fact would inhibit any provision of negative ancillary services by demand units. In order to support demand units, the peak charges for provision of ancillary services are reduced to less than 10% of the normal value, which is regulated in the Electricity System Charges Ordinance [8] Section 5 (9). This rule does not include participation in day ahead and intraday markets, thus offering negative flexibility to energy markets is still impeded by the peak load tariffs in many cases.

An additional barrier for provision of negative balancing services arises from the Green Electricity Act [10] Section 48 (2), which regulates the rate of *renewables contribution* (Ökostromförderbeitrag) for consumers in relation to the network tariffs explained above. The the renewables contribution to be paid by consumers consists of energy and peak rates, which are updated by an ordinance [11,12] every year. The peak rates are only depending on the network level of the connected consumer but do not consider reduced rates for the provision of ancillary services. As a consequence, the currently implemented rules for renewables contribution penalize the provision of negative balancing services. A major increase of the rates of renewables contribution were stipulated for 2020. E.g. for the network level 5 (mid voltage) the renewables contribution for peak consumption was increased from 6,377 EUR/kW/year for 2019 to 10,306 EUR/kW/year. The fact, that the renewables contribution has been increased by more than 60%, highlights the economic difficulties for MES to offer negative flexibility to any power markets. As conclusion, the renewables contribution which was introduced to support renewable generators impedes MES from providing flexibility required for the integration of renewables into the power system.

Additionally, all final consumers have to pay a value added tax of 20% on all cost components (energy, grid tariffs, renewable support, energy charge), which may have impact on privately operated MES but rather not on industrial MES.

Finally, the impact of peak charges for electricity consumption are demonstrated by a simple example for an industrial consumer connected to network level 5 in Lower Austria. The peak charges for this region were defined in 2019 as shown in Table 1. In 2019 an additional consumption peak of 1 MW caused monthly costs of ca. 3 977 EUR in the energy market or 770 EUR in case of ancillary service provision.

Table 1: Peak load charges for consumers in network level 5 in Lower Austria.

	Yearly rate	Monthly costs for +1 MW
System utilisation charge (Netznutzungsentgelt)	39,00 €/kW	3 312 EUR
<i>System utilisation charge for ancillary services</i>	<i>1,00 €/kW</i>	<i>85 EUR</i>
Renewables contribution (Ökostromförderbeitrag)	6,377 €/kW	542 EUR
Biomass contribution (Biomasseförderung)	1,69 €/kW	144 EUR
Sum		3 997 EUR
<i>Sum (for ancillary services)</i>		<i>770 EUR</i>

Assuming a margin of 10 EUR/MWh, the MES would need to consume energy from the intraday market for a duration of 400 h per month, which of course is not feasible.

Assuming the participation of the MES in the negative mFRR market in Austria with an average reserve fee of 1,5 EUR/MW/h and -400 EUR/MWh (about the average market price in December 2019) the MES could have earned 1116 EUR for reserve and 1200 EUR for 3 h of activation in Dec. 2019, i.e. 2316 EUR in total. Considering only the peak load charges of 770 EUR, the net revenues of the MES would already decrease to 1546 EUR, which means a reduction of 33%. Assuming the increased renewables contribution for 2020, the net revenues would even decrease by 48%.

4 Summary

Industrial MES like paper mills can provide flexibility services to existing ancillary service markets or to the intra-day market. It was possible to build a precise model of the CHP and steam system of a paper mill. By means of this model the possible flexibility provision of the MES depending on the state of operation could be quantified as operational boundaries for upward and downward regulations. The result show that the steam system has more capacities for downward regulations than upward regulations, which indicates different capabilities in providing services like aFRR and mFRR to the market. In the next step the improvement of the steam system by the installation of a steam accumulator will be investigated in terms of steam losses, network cost savings, and additional flexibility provision.

While the technologies of steam systems and steam accumulators seem to be well proven, some tariffs for system utilisation and renewables contribution might yet be improved to better support the participation of industrial (net) consumers of electricity in markets for electrical flexibility.

In particular, provision of negative balancing energy will result in an increase of consumption and may cause additional consumption peaks. The operator of the industrial facility will be charged for additional peak consumption on monthly basis according to the Electricity System Charges Ordinance [8] Section 5. Section 5 (9) regulates the *system utilisation charge* for balancing service providers at a fairly reduced rate. Unfortunately, this reduced rate is only available for balancing service provision but does not apply for any schedules related to day-ahead or intraday markets.

An additional barrier for provision of negative balancing services arises from the Green Electricity Act [10] Section 48 (2), which regulates the rate of *renewables contribution* (Ökostromförderbeitrag) for consumers and also sets peak rates for consumers. These peak rates are only depending on the network level of the connected consumer but do not consider reduced rates for the provision of ancillary services. As a consequence, the currently implemented rules for renewables contribution penalize the provision of negative balancing services. This fact may hinder the integration of renewable energies into the power system.

5 Literature

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